

Receiving Phased Antenna Array based on Injection-Locked Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixers

S. Ver Hoeye, Member, IEEE, C. Vázquez, M. Fernández, L.F. Herrán, and F. Las-Heras, Member, IEEE.

University of Oviedo, Signal Theory and Communications Area, Department of Electrical Engineering, Gijón,

E-33204 Spain (phone: +34 985-182-616; fax: +34 985-182-466; e-mail: sverhoeye@tsc.uniovi.es).

Abstract—In this work, a 4×1 element receiving Phased Antenna Array is presented with phase-shifter elements based on Injection-Locked Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixers. Each phase-shifter element provides the double functionality of variable phase-shifter and down-converter. The phase-shifts applied to the input signals coming from the different antenna patch elements can be selected by DC control signals in a continuous range of 450°. The required DC control voltages are calculated for the different incident angles by means of harmonic balance simulations. The influences of phase-shift and conversion gain errors on the beam-steering frequency performance of the antenna are studied. Also is illustrated how the phase-shifter parameters can be optimized in order to minimize the beam-steering errors for different input-frequencies. A 4×1 element receiving phased antenna array, with an input frequency band centered at 11.25 GHz and the output frequency band centered at 1.5 GHz, has been manufactured for the experimental validation of the simulated results. A beam scanning range from -23° to 23° has been experimentally obtained.

Index Terms—Phased arrays, beam steering, shaped beam antennas, microwave phase shifters, injection locked oscillators.

I. INTRODUCTION

For beam-scanning in phased antenna arrays, low cost phase-shifters are required, enabling the control of the phase distribution on the array with simple control circuitry. In the literature, different approaches have been presented for the design of phased arrays based on oscillator circuits [1]-[13]. Phase-shifters based on oscillators that are injection-locked at the first harmonic component of the self-oscillation enable a phase-shift variation with a theoretical range

limited to 180° [1]-[10]. This range is improved to 360° when using a two stage solution where the second oscillator is injection-locked with the second harmonic component of the oscillating signal of the first oscillator [11], or when using a configuration based on master-slave cascaded oscillators [12]. Larger phase shift ranges can be obtained with more complex configurations using frequency multipliers in cascade with the oscillator based phase-shifter [13]. These theoretical ranges are reduced to an about 15% smaller experimentally observable stable phase-shift ranges. Moreover, due to the appearance of noise-precursors when operating at the limits of the stable phase-shift range [14], the usable phase-shift range is generally further reduced to 70% of the theoretical range.

In this work, in order to be able to feed individually the different antenna patches with any phase-shift between 0 and 360° , a new type of variable phase-shifter is used based on an Injection-Locked Third Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixer (IL3HSOM) [15]. The phase-shifters based on IL3HSOM circuits provide in a single oscillator stage a theoretical phase-shift range of 540° which assures a usable range of at least 360° . The desired phase-shift is introduced by means of a mixing operation between the input signal at frequency f_{in} and the third harmonic component at frequency $3f_0$ of the HSOM self-oscillation with fundamental frequency f_0 , resulting in a down-converted signal at the desired output frequency $f_{IF} = f_{in} - 3f_0$ [15]. The IL3HSOM circuit is optimized with the nonlinear techniques presented in [16]-[18], through the use of a multi-harmonic load [19], in order to provide maximum conversion gain in the whole input frequency band. Since the IL3HSOM circuits are efficiently injection locked at the first harmonic component of the self-oscillation, a large number of IL3HSOM based phase-shifters can be synchronized with a single reference generator through a power divider distribution network. A good selection of the self-oscillating frequency and thus of its harmonic components, located out of the input- and output frequency bands, enables to avoid mutual coupling of the IL3HSOM circuits through the antenna simply by filtering, without affecting the conversion gain of the circuits.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the topology of the 4×1 element receiving Phased Antenna Array is presented and the individual behavior of an IL3HSOM and the 4×1 element Antenna Array are studied. In Section III, the beam-scanning performance of the receiving antenna is illustrated, the beam-steering errors are calculated, and the reduction of these errors by means of the optimum synchronization power selection of the IL3HSOM circuits is demonstrated. In Section IV, the experimental results obtained with the manufactured receiving Phased Antenna Array are shown.

II. PHASED ANTENNA ARRAY BASED ON IL3HSOM

A. Topology of the Phased Antenna Array

The topology of the receiving Phased Antenna Array is shown in Fig. 1(a). The Antenna Array consists of four patch antenna elements feeding four IL3HSOM based variable phase-shifters with the received input signal at $f_{in} = 11.1 - 11.4$ GHz. All IL3HSOM circuits are injection locked through a Wilkinson divider with the same external synchronization generator, with power P_s , frequency f_s and phase ϕ_s , at the first harmonic component of the self-oscillation with frequency $f_0 = f_s = 3.25$ GHz. Using the techniques presented in [16]-[18], the IL3HSOM circuits have been optimized in order to provide maximum conversion gain, in the input-frequency band at $f_{in} = 11.1 - 11.4$ GHz, for the mixing operation $f_{IF} = f_{in} - 3f_0$. The phase distribution along the array at the output frequency f_{IF} is measured by means of coupling networks providing a sample of the output signals of the different IL3HSOM circuits to a 4×1 microwave switch (Fig. 1(a)). The phase distribution along the array is measured one by one with a Vector Signal Analyzer by changing the commutation state of the switch. The output signal at f_{IF} of the receiving antenna array is obtained through a Wilkinson combiner and measured with the Vector Network Analyzer from the anechoic chamber measurement setup (Fig. 1(a)). Mutual coupling between IL3HSOM circuits at harmonic components of the self-oscillation Nf_0 ($N = 1$ to 8) is avoided by means of the band-pass filters at the input and output ports, centered at 11.25 GHz and 1.5 GHz respectively (Fig. 1(b)). At the synchronization port, mutual coupling at harmonic components Nf_0 ($N = 2$ to 8) is avoided by means of the band-pass filter at f_0 (Fig. 1(b)). This filter, together with the Wilkinson divider (Fig. 1(a)), are designed to avoid mutual coupling at f_0 and to assure that the reference signal of the different IL3HSOM circuits is determined by the external synchronization generator. Note that due to the fact that the input and output signal frequency bands don't coincide with the harmonic components of the self-oscillation, the mutual coupling between IL3HSOM can be eliminated through filtering without reducing the overall conversion gain. In case a harmonic component of the self-oscillation fell into the input or output frequency band, due to the generally insufficient isolation between antenna array ports and adjacent input-ports of the Wilkinson combiner, it would be necessary to use additional attenuators to avoid mutual coupling between the oscillator circuits, leading to a severe reduction of the output signal power.

B. Antenna Array

A four element microstrip antenna array has been designed on a 0.762 mm thick ARLON N25 substrate with a relative dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r = 3.38$. The antenna elements are identical inset-fed rectangular patches as shown in Fig. 1(c). Two slightly longer parasitic elements have been added to the rectangular patches in order to obtain impedance matching in the 11.1-11.4 GHz input-frequency band. The separation between successive elements of the array has been chosen to be 0.7 wavelengths at 11.25 GHz in free-space.

Fig. 1. (a) Topology of the receiving Phased Antenna Array. (b) Circuit topology of an Injection Locked Third Harmonic Self-Oscillating mixer, with inclusion of an AG generator for optimization purposes. (c) Manufactured four element microstrip antenna array.

C. Behavior of IL3HSOM-based phase-shifters

The phase-shift $\Delta\phi$ between the external synchronization generator signal and the self-oscillation signal of the third harmonic self-oscillating mixer is varied by means of the DC varactor control voltage (V_{cont}). The different injection locked solutions of the IL3HSOM for different power values P_s of the synchronization generator and the corresponding stable phase-shift ranges are calculated with the nonlinear analysis techniques presented in [15], based on the use of an auxiliary generator in harmonic balance and envelope transient simulations. For input frequency $f_{\text{in}} = 11.25$ GHz, the resulting stable and unstable phase-shift ranges obtained at the IL3HSOM output versus the varactor control voltage are presented in Fig. 2 (a). The corresponding variation of the conversion gain G_c is shown in Fig. 2(b). From Fig. 2, it can be seen that, for higher values of P_s , a stronger variation of the varactor control voltage and thus of the varactor capacitance is required (Fig. 2(a)). This leads to a variation of the conversion gain along the phase-shift range which is stronger for higher values of P_s (Fig. 2(b)). For different phase-shift values $\Delta\phi(f_{\text{in},c})$ set at the central input frequency $f_{\text{in},c} = 11.25$ GHz, the frequency response of the phase shift $\Delta\phi$ and the conversion gain G_c are shown in Fig. 3. Considering that for every value of the phase shift $\Delta\phi(f_{\text{in},c})$, the required varactor control voltage V_{cont} is calculated at the central input frequency $f_{\text{in},c}$, then the phase-shifts at other frequencies of the input-frequency band obtained for these values of V_{cont} , are different. This is shown in Fig. 3(a) where $\Delta\phi(f_{\text{in}})$ is represented for

Fig. 2. Behavior of IL3HSOM-based phase-shifters at the input frequency $f_{\text{in}}=11.25$ GHz . (a) Stable and unstable phase-shift ranges obtained at the IL3HSOM output versus the varactor control voltage. (b) Variation of the conversion gain G_c along the phase-shift range.

Fig. 3. Frequency response of the IL3HSOM-based phase-shifters for different values of $\Delta\phi(f_{in,c})$. (a) Variation of the frequency response of the phase shift $\Delta\phi(f_{in})$. (b) Variation of the frequency response of the conversion gain $G_c(f_{in})$.

different values of $\Delta\phi(f_{in,c})$. A stronger slope variation of $\Delta\phi(f_{in})$ with respect to f_{in} is found for higher values of the synchronization power P_s . Also a stronger variation of the conversion gain with respect to f_{in} is obtained for higher P_s values, which is more pronounced at the limits of the input-frequency band (Fig. 3(b)).

III. BEAM SCANNING WITH THE PHASED ANTENNA ARRAY

A. Beam Scanning using a progressive phase-distribution.

Considering the IL3HSOM based phased array of Fig. 1(a), beam scanning operation is achieved by varying the different varactor control voltages $V_{cont,i}$ ($i = 1$ to 4) in order to obtain the required phase-distribution to receive the incident wave under the angle θ_m for which maximum output power is found at f_{IF} (Fig. 4). If the different incident angles θ_m are obtained by means of a progressive phase-distribution $\Delta\phi_i = (2i-5)\Delta\phi_p/2$ along the different elements of the antenna array, with $\Delta\phi_p$ the phase-difference between two consecutive elements, then the different varactor control voltages $V_{cont,i}$ can be calculated for different values of $\Delta\phi_p$. The varactor control voltages $V_{cont,i}$ with respect to $\Delta\phi_p$ for the central input frequency $\Delta\phi_i = \Delta\phi_i(f_{in,c})$, calculated with harmonic balance simulation techniques [15], are shown in Fig. 5(a) for the values of $P_s = -30$ dBm and -40 dBm. The corresponding variation of the incident angle θ_m is shown in Fig. 5(b). In Fig. 5(c) are shown the simulated radiation patterns corresponding with the varactor control voltages $V_{cont,i}$ calculated at $f_{in,c} = 11.25$ GHz for $\theta_m = -25^\circ, -20^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, -5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$. The

Fig. 4. Arrangement of the phased-array elements.

beam scanning range is limited between -23.5° and 23.5° . For θ_m values out of this range, the side-lobe to main-lobe ratio is found to be superior to -10 dB.

Considering the antenna array presented in Fig. 4, with $G_{c,i} = G_c$ ($i = 1$ to 4), and that the values of $\Delta\phi_i$ calculated at $f_{in,c}$ for a particular value of the incident angle θ_m , remain unchanged when varying f_{in} along the input-frequency band, then for other input frequencies $f_{in} \neq f_{in,c}$, the maximum of the radiation pattern theoretically will change with f_{in} as follows:

$$\theta_m(f_{in}) = \arcsin\left(\frac{f_{in,c}}{f_{in}} \sin \theta_m(f_{in,c})\right) \quad (1)$$

In order to avoid the deviation between $\theta_m(f_{in} \neq f_{in,c})$ and $\theta_m(f_{in,c})$ the progressive phase-shift between successive elements should vary with respect to f_{in} . As has been shown in Fig. 3(a) of section II, when maintaining constant the varactor control voltages $V_{cont,i}$ of the IL3HSOM based phase-shifters, obtained for a particular incident angle θ_m at $f_{in,c}$, then the phase distribution $\Delta\phi_i(f_{in})$ for input frequencies f_{in} different from the central frequency $f_{in,c}$, will change with respect to $\Delta\phi_i(f_{in,c})$, leading to a variation of the progressive phase difference $\Delta\phi_p(\theta_m, f_{in})$ with respect to f_{in} that is stronger for higher values of θ_m . This variation, together with the variation of the conversion gain with respect to f_{in} , which is also stronger for higher values $\theta_m(f_{in,c})$ (Fig. 3(b)), leads to a variation of $\theta_m(f_{in} \neq f_{in,c})$ as shown in Fig. 5(b). Depending on the frequency behavior of the used IL3HSOM based phase-shifters, the beam scanning error with respect to the input frequency can be reduced through a good selection of the synchronization power.

Fig. 5. Beam scanning behavior using a progressive phase-distribution, for $P_s = -30$ dBm and -40 dBm. (a) Varactor control voltages $V_{\text{cont},i}(f_{\text{in},c})$ with respect to $\Delta\phi_p(f_{\text{in},c})$. (b) Variation of the incident angle θ_m with respect to $\Delta\phi_p(f_{\text{in},c})$ for different values of the input-frequency f_{in} . (c) Radiation patterns corresponding with the values of $V_{\text{cont},i}(f_{\text{in},c})$ calculated for $\theta_m(f_{\text{in},c}) = -25^\circ, -20^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, -5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$.

B. Reduction of the beam scanning error.

At a particular value of $\theta_m(f_{\text{in},c})$, the variation of the progressive phase difference and the variation of the conversion gain, both with respect to f_{in} , increase for higher values of the synchronization power P_s . The deviation of the conversion gain $DG_{c,i}(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m) = G_{c,i}(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m) - G_c(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m=0)$ and the phase-shift deviation $D\phi_i(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m) = [\Delta\phi_i(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m) - \Delta\phi_i(f_{\text{in},c},\theta_m)] - [\Delta\phi_i(f_{\text{in}},\theta_m=0) - \Delta\phi_i(f_{\text{in},c},\theta_m=0)]$, at the incident angle $\theta_m(f_{\text{in},c}) = 23.5^\circ$, for $P_s = -40$ dBm and $P_s = -30$ dBm, are illustrated in Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b) respectively. The way these deviations are improving the beam scanning error $\Delta\theta_m(f_{\text{in}})=\theta_m(f_{\text{in}})-\theta_m(f_{\text{in},c})$ is illustrated in Fig. 7. Considering that the values of $\Delta\phi_i$ and G_c remain unchanged when varying f_{in} , the beam scanning error obtained by the theoretical equation (1), is almost linear with respect to f_{in} , along the input-frequency band (Fig. 7). Simulating the real behavior of the antenna and the microstrip

Fig. 6. Deviations of the conversion gain and phase-shift at the incident angle $\theta_m(f_{in,c}) = 23.5^\circ$, for $P_s = -40$ dBm and $P_s = -30$ dBm. (a) Deviation of the conversion gain $DG_{c,i}(f_{in}, \theta_m)$. (b) Phase-shift deviation $D\phi_i(f_{in}, \theta_m)$.

Fig. 7. Beam scanning error $\Delta\theta_m(f_{in})$ versus the input frequency f_{in} at the incident angle $\theta_m(f_{in,c}) = 23.5^\circ$, for $P_s = -40$ dBm and $P_s = -30$ dBm.

feeding lines in an electromagnetic simulator, maintaining constant $\Delta\phi$, and G_c with respect to f_{in} ($DG_{c,i}(f_{in}, \theta_m)=0$ and $D\phi_i(f_{in}, \theta_m)=0$), higher values for the beam scanning error are found. Taking the latter simulation as a reference (continuous line in Fig. 7), the improvement of the beam scanning error due to the deviations of Fig. 6, can be studied. Taking into account only the deviation of the conversion gain $DG_{c,i}(f_{in}, \theta_m) \neq 0$ (considering $D\phi_i(f_{in}, \theta_m)=0$), it can be seen from Fig. 7 that the beam steering error almost remains unchanged for both values of the synchronization power $P_s=-40$ dBm and $P_s=-30$ dBm. If only the phase-shift deviation $D\phi_i(f_{in}, \theta_m) \neq 0$ is taken into account (considering $DG_{c,i}(f_{in}, \theta_m)=0$), a reduction of the beam scanning error is found, which is stronger for the case $P_s=-30$ dBm. If both

the deviations $DG_{c,i}(f_{in},\theta_m)\neq 0$ and $D\phi_i(f_{in},\theta_m)\neq 0$ are taken into account, no observable change in the beam scanning error with respect to the previous case is obtained. With this particular design of the IL3HSOM based variable phase-shifters, a lower beam scanning error is obtained when a -30 dBm synchronization power is selected. For higher values of the synchronization power, stronger deviations $DG_{c,i}(f_{in},\theta_m)\neq 0$ and $D\phi_i(f_{in},\theta_m)\neq 0$ are obtained, which can lead to an overcompensation of the beam scanning error.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to validate the simulated results, a four-element antenna array has been constructed following the topology of Fig. 1(a) and mounted in the frame shown in Fig. 8(a). The behavior of the antenna array has been measured in an anechoic chamber for different values of the progressive phase-distribution $\Delta\phi_i$ using the measurement setup of Fig. 8(b). The Tx Horn of the anechoic chamber is fed with an 11.25 GHz signal by means of a first external Signal Generator (SG) (Fig. 8(b)). The different IL3HSOM circuits are injection-locked through the Wilkinson Divider (Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 8(a)) at their 3.25 GHz self-oscillating frequency with a second external signal generator at that frequency. The progressive phase-distribution $\Delta\phi_i$ for any desired incident angle $\theta_m(f_{in,c})$ is established with the DC Varactor Control Voltage Sources when the incidence direction is $\theta = 0$ and is evaluated through the measurement of the sample signals by means of the Vector Signal Analyzer (Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 8(b)). In order to be able to measure correctly this phase-distribution, the same 10 MHz reference signal is used for the internal oscillators of the Vector Network Analyzer, the Vector Signal Analyzer, and both external Signal Generators (Fig. 8(b)). Once established the phase-distribution, the power received by the antenna array at intermediate frequency, for different incident angles, is measured by the Vector Network Analyzer of the anechoic chamber measurement setup.

The measured beam scanning behavior of the antenna when varying $\Delta\phi_i$ is illustrated in Fig. 9(a) to Fig. 9(f) where the normalized IF output power (NP_{IF}) is represented with respect to θ for the established values of $\theta_m(f_{in,c}) = -25^\circ, -20^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, -5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$. Each pattern of Fig. 9 corresponds with the output power at intermediate frequency normalized to its own maximum value. As predicted by the simulations, the steering range is from -23° to 23° . At higher values of $\theta_m(f_{in,c})$ high values for the sidelobe level are found (Fig. 9(f)). The maximum received IF output power for the different established values of $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=-25^\circ$ to 25° compared to the maximum power received for $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=0$, is represented in Fig. 10. The asymmetrical response in Fig. 10 is due to differences in the behavior of

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Experimental Measurement Setup of the antenna prototype. (a) Manufactured IL3HSOM-based receiving phased antenna array mounted in anechoic chamber. (b) System for the evaluation of the antenna phase-distribution and setup in anechoic chamber for the measurement of the beam scanning behavior.

conversion gain with respect to the phase-shift, found between the different manufactured IL3HSOM based phase-shifters.

When changing the input frequency, for the case $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=23^\circ$ (Fig. 11), the maximum of the received power moves in the same way as predicted in section III. Again for higher values of the synchronization power, a reduction of the beam scanning error is found (Fig. 11).

Fig. 9. Measured beam scanning behavior of the receiving IL3HSOM phased antenna array. Normalized IF output power (NP_{IF}) with respect to θ for the established values of $\theta_m(f_{in,c}) = -25^\circ, -20^\circ, -15^\circ, -10^\circ, -5^\circ, 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$.

V. CONCLUSION

A novel design of a receiving 4x1 element phased antenna array based on Injection-Locked Third Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixers has been presented. It has been demonstrated that the multi-functional IL3HSOM circuits can be very useful as variable phase-shifters providing additional functionalities such as local oscillator signal generation and down-conversion of the input signal, for the realization of compact, low cost and low DC-power consuming receiving systems. With the proposed topology for the phased antenna array, coupling problems between different

Fig. 10. Maximum received IF output power for different established values of $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=-25^\circ$ to 25° compared to the maximum power received for $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=0$.

Fig. 11. Beam variation when changing the input frequency, for the case $\theta_m(f_{in,c})=23^\circ$.

IL3HSOM circuits, generally present in oscillator based phased array systems, have been easily avoided by filtering without affecting the IF output power of the phased antenna array. Simulating the overall behavior of the antenna with nonlinear analysis techniques, using a progressive phase-distribution along the array elements, a continuous beam scanning range between -23.5° and 23.5° has been predicted. When changing the input frequency along the input frequency-band, a beam scanning error has been observed which can be reduced by selecting the optimum power of the external synchronization generator. The experimental behavior obtained with the manufactured receiving phased antenna array has been compared with the simulated results, obtaining a good agreement in the beam scanning behavior at the central input-frequency as well as in the beam scanning error found for other input-

frequencies. The reduction of the latter when increasing the synchronization power has also been observed from the experimental results.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K.D. Stephan, "Inter-Injection-Locked Oscillators for Power Combining and Phased Arrays," *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Techn.*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1017-1025, Oct. 1986.
- [2] K.D. Stephan, W.A. Morgan, "Analysis of Interinjection-Locked Oscillators for Integrated Phased Arrays", *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. AP-35, no. 7, pp. 771-781, 1987.
- [3] A.S. Daryoush, M. Francisco, R. Saedi, D. Polifko, R. Kunath, "Phase control of optically injection locked oscillators for phased arrays", *IEEE MTT-S Digest*, pp. 1247-1250, 1990.
- [4] J. Lin, S.T. Chew, T. Itoh, "A Unilateral Injection-Locking Type Active Phased Array for Beam Scanning, *IEEE MTT-S Digest*, pp. 1231-1234, 1994.
- [5] G. Forma, J.-M. Laheurte, "Design for injection-locked oscillator arrays", *Electronics Letters*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 683-684, April 1998.
- [6] J.-H. Hwang, N.-H. Myung, "A New Beam-Scanning Technique by Controlling the Coupling Angle in a Coupled Oscillator Array", *IEEE Microwave and Guided Wave Letters*, vol. 8, no. 5, May 1998.
- [7] T. Nishimura, N. Ishii, K. Itoh, "Beam Scan Using the Quasi-Optical Antenna Mixer Array", *IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 47, no. 7, pp. 1160-1166, July 1999.
- [8] Y.-H. Chen, T.-H. Chu, "Active Phased Array Using Injection-Locked Oscillators", *IEEE APMC2001 Proc.*, pp. 819-822, 2001.
- [9] J. Shen, L.W. Pearson, "A Design for a Two-Dimensional Coupled Oscillator Beam-Steering Antenna Array", *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 2, 2003.

- [10] R. J. Pogorzelski, "A 5-by-5 Element Coupled Oscillator-Based Phased Array," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1337-1345, Apr. 2005.
- [11] X. Zhang, A.S. Daryoush, "Full 360° Phase Shifting of Injection-Locked Oscillators," *IEEE Microwave and Guided Wave Letters*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 14-16, Jan. 1993.
- [12] I. L. Morrow, P.S. Hall, J.R. James, "Measurement and Modeling of a Microwave Active-Patch Phased Array for Wide-Angle Scanning", *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 45, no. 2, Feb. 1997.
- [13] R. A. York, T. Itoh, "Injection- and Phase-Locking Techniques for Beam Control," *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Techn.*, vol. 46, no. 11, pp. 1920-1929, Nov. 1998.
- [14] S. Ver Hoeye, A. Suárez, S. Sancho, "Analysis of Noise Effects on the Nonlinear Dynamics of Synchronized Oscillators," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 376-378, Sep. 2001.
- [15] S. Ver Hoeye, L.F. Herrán, M. Fernández, F. Las Heras, "Design and Analysis of a Microwave Large-Range Variable Phase-Shifter Based on an Injection-Locked Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixer", *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 342-344, June 2006.
- [16] S. Ver Hoeye, L. Zurdo, A. Suárez, "New Nonlinear Design Tools for Self-Oscillating Mixers," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 337-339, Aug. 2001.
- [17] L.F. Herrán, S. Ver Hoeye, F. Las Heras, "Nonlinear Optimization Tools for the Design of Microwave High-Conversion Gain Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixers," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 16-18, Jan. 2006.
- [18] M. Fernández, S. Ver Hoeye, L.F. Herrán, F. Las-Heras, "Nonlinear Optimization of Wide-Band Harmonic Self-Oscillating Mixers," *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 347-349, May 2008.
- [19] S. Ver Hoeye, F. Ramírez, A. Suárez, "Nonlinear Optimization Tools for the Design of High-Efficiency Microwave Oscillators," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 189-191, May 2004.

Samuel Ver Hoeye (M'05) received the M.Sc. degree in electronic engineering from the University of Gent, Gent, Belgium, in 1999, and the Ph.D. degree from the University of Cantabria, Santander, Spain, in 2002.

He is currently Associate Professor with the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering of the University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain. His main research is focused on nonlinear analysis and optimization of microwave circuits and their application to active antennas.

Carlos Vázquez received the M.Sc. degree in telecommunication engineering from the University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain, in 2007 and he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree.

Since 2007, he has been working as a Research Assistant with the Signal Theory and Communications Area, at the University of Oviedo. His research efforts mainly focus on nonlinear analysis and optimization of microwave circuits to be used in active antennas.

Miguel Fernández received the M. Sc. degree in telecommunication engineering from the University of Oviedo in 2006, and he is currently working towards the Ph.D. degree.

Since 2005, Mr. Fernández worked as a Research Assistant with the Signal Theory and Communications Area, at the University of Oviedo, where he is currently Assistant Professor. His main interest are focused on nonlinear analysis and optimization of microwave circuits to be used in active and phased array antennas.

Luis Fernando Herrán received the Telecommunication Engineering degree from the University of Cantabria, Santander, in 1999, and the Ph.D. degree from the University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain, in 2007.

In 2003, he joined the Department of Electrical Engineering at the University of Oviedo. His research interest includes nonlinear optimization of phased array antennas and the design of RF/microwave subsystems.

Fernando Las-Heras (M'86) received the M.S. degree in 1987 and the Ph.D. degree in 1990, both in telecommunication engineering, from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Madrid, Spain.

From 1988 to 1990, he was a National Graduate Research Fellow. From 1991 to 2000, he was an Associate Professor with the Department of Signals, Systems and Radiocommunications, UPM. From 2001 to 2003, he was an Associate Professor with the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain, pioneering the Area of Theory of Signal and Communications at that University. Since December 2003, he has been a Full Professor at the University of Oviedo where he is presently Vice-dean for Telecommunication Engineering degree at the Polytechnic School of Engineering at Gijón. His main research interests include the analysis and design of antennas, electromagnetic interference (EMI), and the inverse electromagnetic problem with application to diagnostic, measurement, and synthesis of antennas.